

Assessment of Anti-Parkinson's potentials of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs

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Abstract:

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by motor impairments such as tremors, rigidity, and bradykinesia. This study evaluated the anti-parkinsonian effects of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulb (*EECA*) in a haloperidol-induced PD rat model. Rats were assigned to control, haloperidol, standard (Syndopa plus 10 mg/kg, b.w, p.o) and *EECA*-treated groups, receiving 200, or 400 mg/kg of ethanolic *EECA*. Haloperidol (1 mg/kg, i.p) induced Parkinson-like symptoms. Motor function was assessed via Catalepsy block method and Metal bar method, while biochemical and histopathological analyses were evaluated. (Syndopa plus 10 mg/kg, b.w, p.o and *EECA* treatment resulted in dose-dependent improvements in motor coordination and locomotor activity, with the 400 mg/kg dose showed maximum response. Dopamine levels were increased, oxidative stress marker (LPO) was decreased, and antioxidant enzyme activity (SOD, CAT) improved significantly. Histopathology confirmed reduced neuronal degeneration in the striatum and substantia nigra. These findings suggest that *Crinum asiaticum* possesses potent anti-Parkinsonian properties, potentially through antioxidant activity and dopaminergic modulation, and merits further investigation as a natural therapeutic candidate for PD.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease, *EECA*, haloperidol, oxidative stress, dopamine, antioxidant enzymes.

Introduction:

Parkinson's disease (PD) results from the progressive and selective degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) [1, 2]. Parkinson's disease results in bradykinesia, muscle rigidity, rest tremor, and loss of postural balance, as well as various secondary neurological signs such as dementia, sialorrhea [3], soft speech, and trouble swallowing due to uncoordinated movements of the lips and throat [4]. Parkinson's disease is characterized by inhibition of mitochondrial complex-1 [5, 6], various cell damage processes such as excitotoxicity, calcium homeostasis, inflammation, apoptosis, impaired energy metabolism, and protein aggregation [7], and interactions between hereditary and environmental variables [8].

Oxidative stress interferes with dopamine metabolism, resulting in Parkinson's disease. This oxidative damage causes the development of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which leads to neuronal death [9,10]. This was demonstrated by a decreased amount of endogenous antioxidant molecules. These findings highlighted the importance of employing antioxidants as a therapeutic strategy in PD, in addition to other preventive medicines.

The currently existing drug therapies for Parkinson's disease have a variety of adverse effects. As a result, herbal therapies should be considered as alternative/complementary treatments for therapeutic purposes.

Since ancient times, plants have been an ideal source of medicine. Plants have played an important role in sustaining human health and boosting quality of life for thousands of years, and they have also served people as valuable components of medications, flavors, beverages, cosmetics and dyes. In modern times, there has been an increased emphasis on plant study all over the world, and a substantial body of evidence has been gathered to indicate the enormous potential of medicinal plants employed in diverse traditional systems.

Crinum asiaticum (Common name: Asian poison bulb) belongs to the family of Amaryllidaceae, locally known as kesaracettu, is an evergreen herb that is widely distributed throughout India along river beds and also in forest [11]. It is known as spider lily, Crinum lily, poison bulb in English, naagadamani in Ayurveda, bakong in Malaysia, and morabau in Papua New Guinea. Various ethnomedicinal properties have been possessed by this plant and are being utilized in the conventional system of medicine. The *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs' ethnomedicinal uses are bitter, expectorant, laxative, carminative, anthelmintic, aphrodisiac, diuretic, urinary problems, diaphoretic, nauseant, analgesic and anti-inflammatory [12], anti-

obesity [13], emetic [14], anticandidial [15]. Literature reports that the bulbs of *Crinum asiaticum* contain flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids, tannins, and phenols are the major phytoconstituents. Hence *C. asiaticum* was evaluated for its anti-Parkinson's effect using haloperidol induced Parkinson's model in rats.

Materials & Methods:

Collection of Plant Material:

The *Crinum asiaticum* plant was collected from the Tirumala hills, Chittoor district, "Andhra Pradesh, India, and authenticated by Assistant Professor, Prof. Dr. K. Madhava Chetty, Department of Botany, Sri Venkateshwara University, Tirupati" (Voucher Number: 2011, dated 08.08.2017). Furthermore, the plant's drying process was done in complete shade; bulbs were separated and pulverized to obtain a coarse powder.

Animals:

Wistar albino male rats (150-200g) were maintained for 7 days in the animal house of Creative Educational Society's college of Pharmacy, Kurnool under standard temperature conditions ($24^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$) with 60% relative humidity and illuminated 12/24 h. The animals were allowed to acclimatize to laboratory conditions 48 h before the start of the experiment. 6 rats / group were used in all sets of experiments. The animals were allowed free access to drinking water and rat feed⁹. All the protocols Experimental Animals were approved by IAEC with the approval number: IAEC/CESCOP/2025-02-09

Preparation of Extract:

Crinum asiaticum bulbs powder was sieved (0.2 mm) then powder was crammed in a thimble and subjected to extraction by using individual solvents using Soxhlet apparatus. Solvents are selected by increasing polarity namely petroleum ether, diethyl ether, chloroform, ethanol and water were used. The crude *Crinum asiaticum* material was extracted in the ratio of (1:3) i.e. for one part of the powder material three parts of solvent. Extraction process was performed until to get colorless solvent. The evaporated extract was stored in a desiccator.

Preliminary phytochemical analysis:

The extract was subjected to various qualitative tests to determine the presence of various phytoconstituents using reported methods. Alkaloids were tested by Dragendorff, Wagner and Mayer tests, Hagner's test while phenolic and flavonoid were tested by ferric chloride, Shinoda and lead acetate test. Salkowski test was used for the detection of triterpenoid and steroidal saponins. Terpenoids and steroids were detected by vanillin sulphuric acid and Liebermann-Burchard tests. Tannins were tested by ferric chloride test, catechin test and chlorogenic acid test. Glycosides were tested by Keller-Killani test, Legal test, Baljet test and foam test [16]

Acute Toxicity studies:

Acute toxicity studies have been carried out according to OECD-423 guidelines to determine the non-lethal dose. The test procedure was carried out using wistar albino rats with the starting dose of 5mg/kg, body weight and continued upto the dose range of 2000mg/kg, body weight [17].

Anti-Parkinson's Activity:**Experimental Design:**

30 animals were grouped into five, having six in each group (n=6). Group I treated as normal. Group II received haloperidol (1mg/kg, i.p), and Group III received Haloperidol(1mg/kg/I.P & L-Dopa + Carbidopa mg/kg/p.o) respectively, Group IV received *Crinum asiaticum* dose (200mg/kg/p.o)+haloperidol(1mg/kg/p.o),Group V received *Crinum asiaticum* (400mg/kg/p.o) + haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p). After the treatment for 14 days, all five groups of animals underwent the behavioral assessment tests. Then Sacrificed the animal and isolated the striatum of the brains of the animals, and homogenate was prepared using ice-cold phosphate-buffered saline solution and stored in refrigerator for further Bio Chemical Analysis

Treatment Design:

S.no	Group	No. of animals	Treatment
1	Normal	6	Normal saline
2	Control	6	Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)
3	Standard	6	L-Dopa Carbidopa (10 mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)
4	Test 1	6	<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> (200mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)
5	Test 2	6	<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> (400 mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)

Catalepsy behavioral study:

Haloperidol (1.0 mg/kg, i.p.) was used to induce catalepsy, and the animals were evaluated at regular intervals up to 120 minutes using the standard block method. Haloperidol, an antipsychotic agent, produces a moderate cataleptic effect. Catalepsy was scored based on the forced placement of the forelimbs on wooden blocks positioned at heights of 3 cm and 9 cm, with a width of 1 cm. The endpoint of the test was considered when both fore-paws were removed from the block or when the animal moved its head. If the animal failed to correct its posture within 10 seconds, it was considered cataleptic. Syndopa (10 mg/kg, p.o.) was used as the standard drug. *Crinum asiaticum* extract was administered to two different groups (n = 6 in

each group) at doses of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg (p.o.), respectively, one hour prior to the administration of haloperidol.

Stage I – Rat is able to move freely on the table it is placed, score = 0.

Stage II – Rat moves when touched or pushed, score = 0.5.

Stage III – If the rat is unable to correct its posture in 10 s when its front paws are set alternately on a 3 cm high block, the score = 0.5 for each paw with a total 1 score.

Stage IV – Rat could not remove its front paws when placed on a 9 cm high block, score = 1 with a total score = 2 for this stage [18].

Measurement of catalepsy by metal bar test:

Catalepsy score was tested for 4 hours at 30 min intervals after haloperidol administration by gently placing both the fore paw of the rat on a metal bar (diameter 2-5mm suspended 6cm above the table top). The impact of catalepsy was estimated by including the time in seconds until the rodent took both fore paws back to the tabletop, with a most extreme cut-off time of 3 minutes. At long last, scores at various time focuses were added and given as aggregate catalepsy score for correlation reason [19].

Determination Of Anti-Oxidant Parameters:

Estimation of lipid peroxidation (LPO) in brain homogenate

300 microns of 10% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) were added to 150 μ L of each sample and centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 minutes at 40C. Around 300 μ L of the supernatant was incubated with 300 μ L 0.67% thiobarbituric acid at 100C for 25 minutes. The blend was cooled for 5 minutes and the thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) concentration as pink stains was measured in a spectrophotometer at 535 nm [20].

Estimation of superoxide dismutase (SOD)

SOD activity was determined by the method developed by Kakkar et al. 1994 0.1ml of homogenate brain tissue was added to 1.2ml of 0.052M sodium pyrophosphate buffer pH (9.3) followed by addition of 0.1ml of 196 μ M Phenazine methosulphate solution, 0.3ml of Nitro blue tetrazolium (300 μ M) solution, 0.2ml of NADH (790 μ M) solution nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH) - phenazine methosulphate nitro blue tetrazolium formation complex Mixture was incubated for 90sec at 30°C and the reaction was stopped by the addition of 0.1ml glacial acetic acid, add each 4ml n. butanol. The colour formed as the end point of the reaction was extracted into the butanol layer and measured at 520 nm. A control was prepared using 0.1ml of distilled water and 0.1ml of homogenate tissue [21].

Estimation of catalase (CAT)

The tissue was homogenized in isotonic buffer (pH - 7.4) and centrifuged at 1000rpm for 10

minutes. 0.2ml of tissue homogenate added to 1.9ml of 50 μ M phosphate buffer. To this mixture 1ml of freshly prepared 30 μ M hydrogen peroxide was added and was measured spectrophotometrically at 240 nm [22].

Estimation of glutathione reductase (GSH)

To 2 ml of the tissue homogenate and KCl mixture 4 ml of cold distilled water and 1 ml of 50% TCA. Were added and the contents are subjected for centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. After 15minutes 2 ml of the supernatant was collected and to that mixture added 4 ml of 0.4 M Tris buffer (pH 8.9) and 0.1 ml of 0.01 M DTNB, the absorbance was measured at 412 nm against the blank reagent. For blank readings, 2 ml of distilled water was used in the place of tissue homogenate [23].

Total GSH was calculated using the formula: $C_o = (A \cdot D) / E$ Where, A is absorbance at 412 nm, D is dilution factor, and E is the molar extinction coefficient ($C = 13,000 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ CM}^{-1}$); C_o is the concentration of GSH.

Determination of neurotransmitter levels:

Estimation of dopamine

0.05 ml 0.4 M HCl and 0.1 ml EDTA / Sodium acetate buffer (PH6. 9) were added to the 0.2 ml aqueous phase, followed by 0.1 ml iodine solution (0.1 M in ethanol) for oxidation. After 2 minutes, the reaction was stopped by adding 0.1 ml Na₂SO₃ solution. After 1.5 minutes, 0.1 mL of acetic acid is added. The solution was then heated to 100°C for 6 minutes, and when the sample returned to room temperature, the spectrofluorometer was used to read the excitation and emission spectra. Dopamine measurements were taken at 330-375 nm.[24]

Estimation of Acetyl cholinesterase (AchE) Ellman's method

4ml of homogenate is added to a cuvette containing 2.6ml of phosphate buffer (0.1M, pH 8) and 100l of DTNB. The contents of the cuvette were thoroughly mixed, and absorbance was measured in a spectrophotometer at 412nm. The basal reading was taken when absorbance reached a stable value. 20l of acetylthiocholine substrate was added, and the change in absorbance was measured. Change in the absorbance per minute was determined. Protein estimation was done using Folin's method. AchE activity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Acetylcholinesterase activity (M/ml) R} = \frac{\delta \text{ O.D} \times \text{Volume of Assay (5ml)}}{E \times \text{mg of protein}}$$

Where,

Rate of enzyme activity in n' mole of acetylcholine iodide hydrolyzed / min/ mg E Ex-
tinction coefficient 13600 M-1cm-1

$\delta O.D$ = change in absorbance

The final reading of enzyme activity is expressed as μ moles/minute/mg tissue

Histopathological Studies:

The brains from control and experimental groups were fixed with 10% formalin and embedded in paraffin wax and cut into longitudinal section of 5 μ m thickness. The sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin dye for histopathological observation.

Statistical Analysis:

All the values were expressed as mean \pm SEM. Statistical evaluation of the data was done by one-way ANOVA (between control and drug treatments) followed by Tukey multiple comparison test, with the level of significance chosen at $p < 0.001$ using Graph-Pad Prism 5 (San Diego, CA) software.

Results:

Phytochemical studies:

Table 2: Qualitative evaluation of ethanol extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs

Phytoconstituents	Tests	Ethanol extract
Alkaloids	Mayer's test	+
	Wagner's test	+
	Dragendroff's test	+
	Hager's test	+
Glycosides	Keller killani test	-
	Baljet test	-
	Legal's test	-
	Modified Borntrager's test	-
Tannins & Phenolics	Ferric chloride test	-
	Lead acetate test	-
Flavonoids	Shinoda Test	+
Steroids	Liebermann- Burchard test	+
	Chlorosulfonic acid test	+

Terpenoids	Salkowski test	+
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“+” indicates the presence.

“-” indicates the absence

Acute toxicity studies:

The purified and completely dried ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs was subjected for the acute toxicity study to determine the lethal dose using Wistar albino mice in forced environment. Acute toxicity studies were performed according to the OECD 423 guidelines. The *EECA* (2000mg/b.w) was administered by oral route to a group of rats using oral feeding needle (22 gauge). After treatment to rats were monitored for 14 days and it was observed that non changes in normal behavior, hence it was confirmed that the *EECA* is virtually nontoxic in normal rats and fall under the sort of GHS category 5, from that 1/10th of dose (200/kg b.w), 1/5th dose (400mg/kg b.w) from maximum safe dose was considered for further evaluation of pharmacological studies.

Table No: 3 Effect of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs (200mg/kg, & 400mg/kg p.o) On Haloperidol Induced Catalepsy in Rat Brains

Group	Drug treatment	0 min	30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min	150 min	180 min
I	Normal	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0
II	Haloperidol (1 mg/kg/i.p)	0.00±0.00 ^{###}	1.40±0.1 ^{###}	2.50±0.17 ^{###}	2.90±0.09 ^{###}	3.21±0.08 ^{###}	3.10±0.03 ^{###}	2.94±0.05 ^{###}
III	L Dopa + Carbidopa (10 mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)	0.00±0.00	0.51±0.08 ^{**}	1.06±0.19 ^{**}	1.11±0.06 ^{**}	0.98±0.05 ^{**}	0.94±0.06 ^{***}	0.38±0.09 [*]
IV	EECA (200mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)	0.00±0.00	1.24±0.13 ^{**}	1.64±0.07 ^{**}	1.41±0.10 ^{**}	1.39±0.05 ^{**}	0.92±0.06 ^{**}	0.45±0.04 [*]
V	EECA (400mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)	0.00±0.00	0.56±0.06 ^{**}	1.24±0.13 ^{***}	1.14±0.07 ^{**}	0.94±0.058 ^{**}	0.83±0.03 ^{***}	0.34±0.04 [*]

Data represented as mean ± SEM (n = 6), analysed by one-way ANOVA Tukey's multiple comparison test.

Significant difference [#]p < 0.05, ^{##}p < 0.01, ^{###}p < 0.001 in comparison to the control group.

Significant difference ^{*}p < 0.05, ^{**}p < 0.01, ^{***}p < 0.001 in comparison to Haloperidol treated group.

Table No: 4 Effect of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs (200mg/kg, & 400mg/kg p.o) on Behavioral assessment in Haloperidol induced Rats by Metal Bar test

Group	Drug treatment	0 min	60 min	120 min	180 min	240 min
I	Normal	8.26±0.08	8.45±0.13	9.51±0.14	8.57±0.10	6.04±0.18
II	Haloperidol (1 mg/kg/i.p)	15.16±0.10 ^{###}	14.46±0.80 ^{###}	15.96±0.92 ^{###}	13.16±0.83 ^{###}	11.36±0.70 ^{###}
III	L Dopa + Carbidopa (10 mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)	8.42±0.08 ^{***}	8.67±0.70 ^{***}	10.24±0.80 ^{***}	10.96±0.73 ^{***}	6.96±0.57 ^{***}
IV	EECA (200mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)	4.96±0.22 ^{**}	5.96±1.20 ^{**}	7.76±1.20 ^{**}	8.45±0.55 ^{**}	4.46±0.55 [*]
V	EECA (400mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)	7.58±0.17 ^{***}	8.22±2.55 ^{***}	9.16±1.52 ^{***}	10.41±1.07 ^{***}	6.21±0.42 ^{***}

Data represented as mean ± SEM (n = 6), analysed by one-way ANOVA Tukey's multiple comparison test.

Significant difference [#]p < 0.05, ^{##}p < 0.01, ^{###}p < 0.001 in comparison to the control group.

Significant difference ^{*}p < 0.05, ^{**}p < 0.01, ^{***}p < 0.001 in comparison to Haloperidol treated group.

Table No 5: Effect of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs (200mg/kg, & 400mg/kg p.o) on Lpo, Sod, Cat, GSH, Da And Ach Levels in Haloperidol Induced Rat Brain

Group	Drug treatment	LPO (nm/mg protein)	SOD (μ /mg protein)	CATALASE (μ /mg protein)	GSH (μ /mg protein)	DA (ng/mg tissue)	Ach (ng/mg tissue)
I	Normal	5.768 \pm 0.043	8.435 \pm 0.022	3.283 \pm 0.021	12.00 \pm 0.058	9.59 \pm 0.045	5.620 \pm 0.043
II	Haloperidol (1 mg/kg/i.p)	2.637 \pm 0.0360 ^{###}	4.285 \pm 0.0121 ^{###}	1.185 \pm 0.0121 ^{###}	6.067 \pm 0.044 ^{###}	4.570 \pm 0.044 ^{###}	2.637 \pm 0.036 ^{###}
III	L Dopa + Carbidopa (10 mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)	5.358 \pm 0.043 ^{***}	8.028 \pm 0.033 ^{***}	3.050 \pm 0.017 ^{***}	11.10 \pm 0.058 ^{***}	8.687 \pm 0.042 ^{***}	5.358 \pm 0.043 [*]
IV	EECA (200mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)	4.033 \pm 0.041 ^{**}	5.717 \pm 0.0316 ^{**}	1.733 \pm 0.022 ^{**}	8.700 \pm 0.046 ^{**}	6.017 \pm 0.055 ^{**}	4.033 \pm 0.041 [*]
V	EECA (400mg/kg/p.o) + Haloperidol (1mg/kg/i.p)	4.697 \pm 0.039 ^{***}	6.718 \pm 0.028 ^{***}	2.500 \pm 0.026 ^{***}	10.080 \pm 0.038 ^{***}	7.597 \pm 0.045 ^{***}	4.697 \pm 0.039 [*]

Data represented as mean \pm SEM (n = 6), analysed by one-way ANOVA Tukey's multiple comparison test.

Significant difference [#]p < 0.05, ^{##}p < 0.01, ^{###}p < 0.001 in comparison to the control group.

Significant difference *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 in comparison to Haloperidol treated group.

Graph No: 1 Effect of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs (200mg/kg, & 400mg/kg p.o) on Haloperidol Induced Catalepsy in Rat Brains

Graph No.2: Effect of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs (200mg/kg, & 400mg/kg p.o) on Behavioral assessment in Haloperidol induced Rats by Metal Bar test

Graph No 3: Effect of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs (200mg/kg, & 400mg/kg p.o) on Lpo, Sod, Cat, GSH Levels in Haloperidol Induced Rat Brain

Graph No 4: Effect of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs (200mg/kg, & 400mg/kg p.o) on Ach and Dopamine Levels in Haloperidol Induced Ra

Histopathology brains of haloperidol induced Parkinson's rats treated with L dopa + Carbidopa100+25mg/kg) & EECA

Normal group showing
No changes in the brain

Control (Haloperidol 1mg/kg)
Showing degeneration of neurons

Standard (L dopa +
Carbidopa100+25mg/kg)
No degeneration of neurons

Crinum asiaticum (200mg/kg)
showing Less degeneration of
neurons than control group

Crinum asiaticum (400mg/kg)
Showing protection of neurons
similar to that of normal

Figure.1: Histopathology of rat brain

Discussion

Parkinson's disease is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized mainly by motor symptoms such as tremors, rigidity, bradykinesia, and postural instability. These symptoms mainly occur due to the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra region of the brain. In experimental studies, Parkinson-like symptoms can be produced in animals using drugs such as haloperidol. Haloperidol is a dopamine D2 receptor antagonist that blocks dopaminergic transmission in the brain and produces extrapyramidal symptoms similar to Parkinsonism.

In the present study, haloperidol-induced Parkinsonism in rats was used as an experimental model to evaluate the potential anti-Parkinsonian activity of *crinum asiaticum*. Administration of haloperidol resulted in significant motor impairments in the animals, which were observed through behavioral tests such as catalepsy. These results confirm that haloperidol successfully induced Parkinson-like symptoms in the experimental animals. [24-26]

Crinum asiaticum is a naturally occurring phenolic compound found in many plants and dietary sources. It is well known for its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective properties. In this study, treatment with *Crinum asiaticum* showed a noticeable improvement in reduction of cataleptic behavior in rats when compared with the haloperidol control group. This suggests that *Crinum asiaticum* may exert a protective effect against haloperidol-induced parkinsonism in rats.

The observed anti-parkinsonian effect of *Crinum asiaticum* may be attributed to its strong antioxidant activity. Oxidative stress is considered one of the major factors involved in the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in Parkinson's disease. *Crinum asiaticum* may help neutralize free radicals and reduce oxidative damage in neuronal cells. In addition, it may also help in maintaining dopamine levels and protecting neuronal integrity.

The results of this study indicate that ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs significantly improved behavioral parameters in the experimental animals. The effect observed in the ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs treated groups was comparable to the standard drug group, suggesting its potential therapeutic value. These findings support the possibility that ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs could be beneficial in reducing Parkinson-like symptoms induced by dopamine receptor blockade.

Treatment with the standard drug L-Dopa combined with Carbidopa showed improvement in antioxidant enzyme activities and helped restore neurotransmitter balance, confirming its protective effect against haloperidol-induced oxidative damage. [26]

Administration of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs at doses of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg showed a marked improvement in antioxidant status. Both doses increased the levels of SOD, CAT, GSH, and dopamine, while helping to normalize acetylcholine levels in the brain. The 20 mg/kg dose of ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs produced a more pronounced effect compared to the lower dose, indicating a dose-dependent neuroprotective activity. The improvement in antioxidant enzyme levels suggests that ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* bulbs possesses significant antioxidant and neuroprotective properties.

Conclusion:

In view of the above facts, we are presuming that ethanolic extract of *Crinum asiaticum* plant showed to be an antioxidant and exhibited a significant effect in animals with Parkinson's disease. And we realize further specified molecular studies with this drug in anti-Parkinson's pharmacology and toxicology and also characterization of active constituents responsible for neuroprotective effect.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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